

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

September 18, 2025
LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania

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DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

Co-funded by
the European Union

LOGOS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

September, 2025

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The book is part of the series “Open Publications for Society”,
an initiative of LOGOS University College, supported by the consortium
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VALBONA NATHANAILI

LOGOS University College

Dr. Nathanaili is currently a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania, with an experience of more than 35 years in the field of academia and publication. She is a Bachelor in physics and a doctoral degree holders in the science of pedagogy, both from University of Tirana. Major areas of research over the last few years are the politics and reforms in Albanian Education System, methodology of teaching science, university pedagogy, the future of schooling and Recognition and Accreditation of Prior Learning gained after flexible learning paths. She is analyst, writers and contributor for different periodic Albanian newspaper and television outlets. Nathanaili, in collaboration with different HEIs, has been initiator and supporter of STEM national campaigns, to encourage girls to pursue careers in science, technology, engineering and math fields and promote women in those fields. Dr. Nathanaili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects.

KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUMIS

LOGOS University College

Konstantinos Giakoumis is Professor of History, Arts and Didactics at LOGOS University College, where he also leads the Faculty of Humanities and Linguistic Communication. He is a doctoral degree (Ph.D.) holder PhD from the University of Birmingham, serves on the international advisory board of Art Readings (Institute of Art Studies, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences) and reviews for the Serbian Academy of Sciences, the University of Crete, and international journals including *Speculum* (University of Chicago Press), the *Journal of Religious History* (Wiley), and *Politics, Religion & Ideology* (Taylor & Francis). He has also served as coordinator of a number of ERASMUS+ CBHE projects (Roaming, Homo Digitalis, DiLanEdu-WB). For a Marie Curie fellowship application in 2018 he received the European Commission's Seal of Excellence. A prolific scholar, his work appears in leading journals such as *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* (Cambridge), *Turkish Historical Review* (Brill), and the *International Journal of Cultural Policy* (Taylor & Francis). His most recent book examines the Codex of the Diocese/Metropolis of Dryinoupolis and Gjirokastra (1760–1858), published by LOGOS University College Press.

ELONA KARAFILI

POLIS University

Dr. Elona Karafili is an expert in the field of economic development. She is a lecturer and researcher at POLIS University, Tirana, Albania since 2007. She holds a PhD in Urban Planning from Ferrara University and Polis University. Elona currently holds the position of the Deputy Rector of POLIS University. Her main topics of interest and expertise

include regional economic development and territorial competitiveness, which she has explored through a number of projects that focus on place-based innovation. Dr. Karafili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects. She is enthusiastic to strengthen the innovation ecosystem in Albania through fostering co-creative processes, academia–business collaboration and knowledge transfer, startup support and commercialization of research.

DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ

University of Sarajevo

Vice Rector for Quality at the University of Sarajevo and a Professor at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. Her research interests and teaching are focused on software engineering in biomedical and cognitive domains. She is highly motivated to learn about problem domains and committed to achieving a high level of user experience. In addition to teaching and research, she is engaged in various activities aimed at improving education in Bosnia and Herzegovina, especially through promoting student-centered and outcome-based learning and using software as educational content.

BLERTA DRENOFCI (CANI)

LOGOS University College

Dr. Drenofci has devoted her efforts for last 20 years at the Albanian Disability Rights Foundation, to the activities in advocacy and lobbying for disability related policy and legislation adoption and implementation and offering of supportive services for people in need throughout the country. She is an expert in the area of social policies and collaborator in the formulation of policy framework for people with disabilities in Albania. She has directed ADRF contribution in several important legal initiatives. ADRF is acknowledged as the pioneer and leader of human rights-based approach to disability and it is one in the few organizations that offer models of supportive services like mobility means, supported employment, free legal aid for people in need in Albania. Blerta has an PhD in Social Sciences and has an academic background, being a teacher of University of Tirana since 2013. She has been the leader and the author of a lot of studies in the field of social policies in and outside the country. She has been involved as a consultant in the research and policy development by several international agencies. During the years 2014-2022, she has been involved in the development of the new reform for the assessment of disability in Albania, based on international standards.

ARBANA KADRIU

South East European University

Arbana Kadriu is a Full Professor of Computer Science at the Faculty of Contemporary Sciences and Technologies, South East European University (SEEU) in Tetovo, North Macedonia. She earned her PhD in Computer Science from Ss. Cyril and Methodius

University, Skopje (2008), specializing in natural language processing and information retrieval. Her research spans AI and machine learning, software engineering, web information retrieval, social network analysis, and e-learning, with a growing focus on speech technologies for low-resource languages. Prof. Kadriu teaches across undergraduate, master's, and doctoral programs, organized into three clusters: Data & Intelligence, Software & the Web, and Research & Methods. She has supervised numerous master's and PhD theses in areas such as data mining–driven decision support, Albanian speech recognition, authorship analysis, and automatic music generation. Prof. Kadriu has authored 70+ publications across journals and international conferences (IEEE, Springer, PLOS ONE, and others) and contributes to international projects, including Erasmus+ initiatives on digital humanities and quality assurance, as well as COST actions on language technology and language learning.

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DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

SEPTEMBER 18, 2025

Hosted by LOGOS University College

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- University of Patras
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LOGOS University College

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Trends, Challenges and Perspectives

Logos University College, Tirana, Albania

Thursday, September 18, 2025

9.00-9.30	Registration
9.30-10.00	Open remarks
	Ilia Ninka, rector, LOGOS University College
	Gertiola Cepani, Director of Labour Market Services at 'National Employment and Skills Agency'
	Konstantinos Giakoumis, HOMO DIGITALIS Project Coordinator

TOPIC

AUTHOR(S)

OPPONENT

FIRST CONFERENCE TRACK			
Digital Competences in Higher Education and the Labour Market			
10.00-10.20	1. The Impact of Digital Transformation on Human Resource Management. Case Study: Albanian Universities During the Pandemic Period	Emira Spahaj, Edisela Mena, Malvina Hysa, Blerta Avdia	Elona Karafli
10.20-10.40	2. Barriers and Opportunities in Albanian Higher Education for Students with Disabilities: A Mixed-Methods Analysis	Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Valbona Nathaniaili	Merima Muslić
10.40-11.00	3. The Digital Employment Gap in Albania: Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education	Gertjana Hasalla	Arberore Bicaj
SECOND CONFERENCE TRACK			
Institutional Strategies and Policy Development			
11.00-11.20	4. Integrated Technical Assessment and Restoration Strategy for the "Topulli" House: Restoration Strategies, Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies	Nikolla Vesho, Panagiotis Kyriatsis, Ajla Gjoka, Lumturi Haska, Sara Ciba, Migena Gjoni, Ardis Duka, Romir Mazari	Konstantinos Giakoumis
11.20-11.40	5. The Role of MOOCs and Open Educational Resources in Higher Education: Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science	Dorina Minxuri	Valbona Nathaniaili

11.40 -12.00	6. Language Technologies and Digital Humanities for Low-Resource Languages and Communities	Arbana Kadriu, Lejla Abazi-Bexheti	Blerta Drenofci (Çani)
12.00-12.20	Coffee break		
12.20-12.40	7. The Cognitive–Digital Turn in Higher Education. <i>A Longitudinal Analysis of AI Engagement in an Architectural Design Studio</i>	Fulvio Papadhopulli, Megi Tafaj	Nikolaos Avouris
12.40-13.00	8. Defining a Strategic Action Plan for AI in Higher Education	Nikolaos Avouris	Valbona Nathaniaili
13.00-13.20	9. Institutional Policies and Strategic Directions for Advancing Digital Competencies in Higher Education	Hajdin Berisha, Agron Hajdari, Bekim Samadraxha	Flora Krasniqi
THIRD CONFERENCE TRACK			
The intended and attained curriculum			
13.20-13.40	10. Digital Competencies in Social Sciences – A Pilot Study. <i>From Design to Practice: Teaching Approaches in the HOMO DIGITALIS Project</i>	Valbona Nathaniaili, Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Konstantinos Giakoumis, Dušanka Bošković, Arbana Kadriu, Anisa Duka	Bujar Gallopeni
13.40-14.00	11. Enhancing Learning through Multimedia Cultural Heritage Applications: Managing Cognitive Load	Merima Muslić, Dušanka Bošković, Vensada Okanović, Selma Rizvić	Blerta Avdia
14.00-14.20	12. Integrating Digital Competencies into Higher Education Curricula. <i>A Case Study from LOGOS University College within the Homo Digitalis Project</i>	Juna Muça, Anxhela Laska, Elpiniqi Merkuri, Edvaldo Begotaraj	Emira Spahaj
14.20-15.40	Lunch		
20.00-22.00	Social Dinner and Awarding of Certificates of Participation and Presentation of Papers		

**PART ONE:
DIGITAL COMPETENCES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION
AND THE LABOUR MARKET**

INTEGRATED TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT AND RESTORATION STRATEGY FOR THE ‘TOPULLI’ HOUSE

Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies

Nikolla VESHO^{1*}, Panagiotis KYRATSIS²,
Ajla GJOKA², Lumturi HASKA², Sara CIBA²,
Migena GJONI², Ardis DUKA³, Romir MAZARI⁴

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Abstract

This research investigates the application of advanced digital technologies in the documentation, analysis, and conservation of this vernacular-built heritage, with a specific focus on the Cerciz Topulli House in Gjirokastra, Albania. Recognized as a key architectural and historical asset within the UNESCO World Heritage Site, the structure exemplifies 19th-century fortified domestic architecture characteristic of the region. The study was conducted as part of a collaborative restoration initiative in November 2024, involving the Faculty of Architecture, local governance units, and UNESCO. A multi-scale, data-driven methodology was implemented, integrating traditional architectural survey techniques with state-of-the-art tools including UAV-based photogrammetry, terrestrial laser scanning, and hybrid workflows in Building Information Modeling (BIM) and (hBIM). Detailed 3D geometric documentation facilitated structural assessments through finite element modeling (FEM), enabling the identification of material vulnerabilities and deformation patterns. Parametric modeling and digital reconstruction supported scenario-based analyses for future conservation planning. This interdisciplinary framework combining architectural heritage, structural diagnostics, and digital preservation demonstrates the efficacy of technologically enhanced approaches in safeguarding at-risk cultural assets. The outcomes contribute a replicable methodological model for heritage conservation in seismic and climatically sensitive contexts across the Balkan region.

Keywords: Restoration camp, metric survey, laser scanner, hBIM, Topulli house, heritage revitalization;

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

NIKOLLA VESHO

Ph.D. Ing. Nikolla Vesho is a Lecturer at the Faculty of Architecture and Design, Polis University, where he has been teaching for over 6 years. He also serves as a faculty member in the Executive Master’s Program in Restoration, Conservation, and Valorization of Cultural Heritage, a joint initiative between the University of Ferrara (Italy) and Polis University (Albania). Dr. Vesho’s teaching and research activities encompass ‘Structural Engineering I & II’, ‘Theory of Structures’, ‘Engineering Statics’, ‘Restoration of Cultural Heritage’, and ‘Structural Rehabilitation and Strengthening’. He has played a central role in introducing ‘Building Information Modeling (BIM)’ into architectural and engineering curricula, linking digital survey methods with conservation practice. His doctoral research investigates the optimization of restoration traditions by integrating algorithmic programming with innovative computational workflows, including BIM, MEP, and FEM tools. He has published in the areas of seismic engineering and earthquake-resistant design, while also contributing to post-earthquake investigations following the November 2019 Albania earthquake in Durrës and Tirana, where he collaborated with expert teams and involved students in technical fieldwork. Alongside his academic career, since 2020 Dr. Vesho has gained professional experience in construction and structural design companies in Albania and Greece, where he has contributed to the design and evaluation of masonry and reinforced concrete structures, as well as heritage rehabilitation projects. Between October 2021 and June 2022, he undertook research mobility at Tor Vergata University of Rome (UniRoma2) under Prof. Donato Abruzzese and at the Polytechnic University of Bari, contributing to teaching Structural Engineering II under Prof. Aguinardo Fraddosio.

PANAGIOTIS KYRATSI

Dr. Panagiotis Kyratsis (www.kyratsis.com) is Professor of the Department of Product and Systems Design Engineering, University of Western Macedonia, Greece. He is the Director of the Institute of Traditional Architecture and Cultural Heritage, University Research Center “TEMENUS” and the Director of the Computational Design and Digital Fabrication Research Lab (CODE+). Prof. Panagiotis Kyratsis received his PhD in CAD-based manufacturing process simulations from the Department of Production Engineering and Management, Technical University of Crete, Greece. He holds a diploma in Mechanical Engineering from the Aristotle’s University of Thessaloniki - Greece, and he received his M.Sc. in Automotive Product Engineering and M.Sc. in CAD/CAM from Cranfield University, UK. He has been involved in several industrial projects, and he has a great deal of expertise in both the design and the manufacturing aspects of product development. His main research interests include manufacturing/machining, CAD/CAM/CAE systems, computational design, Artificial Intelligence (AI), additive manufacturing (AM), CAD-based applications, product design, reverse engineering and prototyping. He has published more than 20 books and more than 200 papers in Scientific Journals and

International Conferences. He acts as member of the editorial board and reviewer to numerous scientific journals and holds 12 industrial designs and two patents registered within the Greek Patent Office.

AJLA GJOKA

Ajla Gjoka is a final-year student at the Faculty of Architecture and Design, Polis University, Tirana. Over the course of her academic journey, she has cultivated a strong foundation in architectural theory and practice, enriched by diverse professional and extracurricular experiences. She has actively participated in several workshops and competitions, including a national design competition where her team won first prize, an achievement that reflects both her creativity and collaborative skills. In 2024, she joined a restoration camp in Gjirokastrë, contributing to the conservation of the historic Topulli House and gaining valuable hands-on experience in heritage preservation. Currently, Ajla is employed at an architecture studio in Tirana, where she is involved in ongoing design and construction projects, further developing her technical expertise and professional competence. Her international exposure includes participation in a summer school in Italy, organized in collaboration with the Universities of Reggio Calabria and Naples. The project, Sulieia, adopted an interdisciplinary approach to urban and architectural challenges and continues to inform her academic research, laying the groundwork for her diploma thesis. Driven by a passion for design innovation, cultural heritage, and sustainable architecture, Ajla aspires to build a career dedicated to creating meaningful, context-sensitive, and resilient built environments.

LUMTURI HASKA

Lumturi Haska, 22, originally from Gjirokastra, is a fifth-year architecture student at Polis University, Albania. Deeply passionate about architecture, cultural heritage, and design innovation, she actively combines academic studies with practical experience, aiming to bridge theoretical knowledge with real-world applications. She has participated in several international Tirana Architecture Weeks (TAW) workshops, where her creativity and commitment to architectural design were recognized with a first-prize award in one edition. In addition, she took part in two consecutive Restauro Camps in Gjirokastra (2023 and 2024), engaging directly with restoration and conservation practices. These immersive experiences not only enhanced her technical skills but also reinforced her dedication to the preservation of architectural heritage and historic urban environments. Her professional journey began in 2024 with an internship at a local architectural studio, where she translated academic knowledge into practice by contributing to active projects. Building on this foundation, she continues to work at the same studio throughout 2025, expanding her skills in design development, documentation, and project implementation. Looking ahead, Lumturi aspires to pursue a career that integrates professional practice with academic research, with a strong focus on restoration, sustainable design, and the conservation of cultural heritage. At 22, she is committed to advancing her expertise and contributing meaningfully to both her community and the broader architectural profession.

SARA CIBA

Sara is a fifth-year student at the Faculty of Architecture and Design, Polis University, Tirana. As part of her academic training, she actively participated in the Restoration Camp in Gjirokastër, where she contributed to the documentation and observation of historic monuments. This experience offered her valuable, hands-on exposure to conservation practices, strengthening her understanding of fundamental methods for preserving and restoring cultural heritage within its authentic context. Her academic interests center on sustainable architecture, the conservation of built heritage, and the integration of contemporary digital tools such as photogrammetry and BIM into design and documentation processes. Through her studies and practical experiences, she has developed an interdisciplinary perspective that combines architectural design, heritage conservation, and technological innovation. Sara aims to further advance in the field of architecture by contributing to projects that promote cultural continuity while addressing contemporary needs, ensuring a balance between tradition, sustainability, and modern practice.

MIGENA GJONI

Migena Gjoni is a fifth-year student at POLIS University, enrolled in the Architecture and Urban Design program. Her academic focus lies in integrating theory with practice to design sustainable spaces that balance functionality, cultural relevance, and human well-being. She has actively participated in a range of academic and professional initiatives, most notably the restoration camp in the historic city of Gjirokastër. During this project, she contributed to the surveying, documentation, and presentation of the existing structure, as well as the identification of necessary structural interventions. Her work further extended to the development of a restoration and adaptive reuse proposal, an experience that refined her technical skills in structural analysis, conservation strategies, and context-sensitive architectural design. In addition to academic engagements, Migena has undertaken internships and collaborations with architectural studios, where she has worked on both collaborative and independent projects. These experiences have allowed her to apply university knowledge in professional contexts, deepening her ability to link architectural design with cultural, social, and environmental dimensions. Her professional ambition is to advance in the fields of architecture and urban design, with a particular commitment to creating spaces that honor cultural heritage while fostering sustainable and innovative opportunities for contemporary urban development.

ARDIS DUKA

Ardis Duka is a civil engineer and currently serves as the Director of the Regional Directorate of Cultural Heritage in Gjirokastër, a position he has held for more than two and a half years. He has substantial experience in the restoration, conservation, and management of cultural monuments, coordinating major projects dedicated to the preservation and valorization of tangible heritage in southern Albania. Following his undergraduate degree in Civil Engineering, he pursued an Executive Master's in Monument Restoration and

Heritage Valorization, strengthening his technical expertise with advanced training in heritage conservation. His professional work emphasizes the integration of modern conservation methodologies with traditional construction techniques, ensuring both structural resilience and authenticity in restoration practices. In addition to his technical and managerial responsibilities, Mr. Duka actively promotes cultural heritage as a catalyst for sustainable community development, advocating for its role in fostering local identity, education, and cultural tourism. His leadership at the Regional Directorate has positioned him at the intersection of engineering, heritage management, and cultural policy, contributing to the safeguarding and revitalization of one of Albania's most significant historical regions.

ROMIR MAZARI

Romir Mazari is a graduate architect from Polis University, Albania. He holds a Professional Master's degree in Cultural Heritage from the Polytechnic University of Tirana and a Master of Science degree in Archaeology from the University of Tirana. In 2024, he further completed a Master of Science in Agro-Environmental Engineering at the Agricultural University of Tirana. Currently, he is engaged as a partner at Grama shpk, a company active in the fields of construction, cultural heritage, and environmental projects. Previously, he worked at the National Institute of Cultural Heritage in Albania, where he contributed to the documentation, conservation, and management of architectural heritage. In parallel with his professional practice, he serves as an external lecturer at Polis University, where he shares his expertise with architecture students in heritage-related courses. His professional experience spans across architecture, archaeology, construction, and environmental studies, with a particular focus on the preservation and sustainable management of cultural heritage assets. His research and professional interests include monument conservation, restoration practices, and the integration of environmental considerations into heritage management strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Situated in southern Albania, the historic city of Gjirokastra was recognized by UNESCO in 2005 for its outstanding example of Ottoman-era urban fabric in the Balkans. The city's traditional architecture carefully adapted to the steep terrain of the Drino Valley offers valuable perspectives on historical urban life and cultural continuity in the region.

Efforts to safeguard its architectural heritage began in 1961, when Gjirokastra was declared a "museum city," leading to the official protection of over 600 traditional structures from a total of 1,220 [30, 26]. The city's form and construction practices evolved in direct response to its mountainous setting, climatic conditions, and socio-economic context [20]. Central to Gjirokastra's architectural identity are the tower houses multi-functional buildings that combined domestic and defensive roles. These structures, commissioned during the Ottoman period and built by skilled artisans from surrounding regions, symbolize the city's former wealth and regional importance [4, 10, 17].

Historic settlements such as Gjirokastra, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, embody a unique synthesis of urban morphology, vernacular architecture, and traditional construction techniques. Characterized by steep topography, stone-paved alleys, and a dense fabric of fortified tower houses, the city reflects centuries of socio-cultural layering and architectural adaptation. These buildings, typically constructed with local limestone, wood-framed upper floors, and slate roofs structure, represent a remarkable integration of structural ingenuity and aesthetic identity within a challenging terrain [4, 17].

The architectural value of Gjirokastra lies not only in its individual monuments but in the coherence of its urban ensemble, shaped by Ottoman-period spatial organization and adapted to the mountainous landscape [4]. Restoration efforts must therefore engage with the material authenticity and typological complexity of the built environment preserving original elements such as carved stone details, wooden ceilings, and traditional ventilation systems, while addressing structural vulnerabilities arising from age, seismic risk, and environmental degradation [10, 15].

This study focuses on the restoration of architectural heritage in Gjirokastra, highlighting the need for context-sensitive methodologies that combine historical research, building diagnostics, and compatible material interventions [36]. It aims to contribute to a sustainable conservation model that reinforces both the physical integrity and cultural significance of the city's historic fabric. Beyond its conservation focus, the study also highlights the pedagogical dimension of digital heritage tools. Integrating methods such as BIM, photogrammetry, and parametric simulation within Higher Education enhances students' digital literacy and critical problem-solving skills, preparing future professionals to address heritage conservation with both technical competence and cultural sensitivity.

'TOPULLI' HOUSE, ARCHITECTURAL AND HISTORICAL REVIEW

The Çerçiz Topulli House, located on the slopes of Dunavat in Gjirokastër, is among the earliest fortified residences built outside the city's medieval castle. Constructed in the early

19th century by Mehmet Topulli, the structure exemplifies the kullë typology traditional tower houses that combined residential and defensive functions, characteristic of Ottoman-influenced Balkan architecture [15] (see Fig. 1a, 1b).

Fig. 1. a) Archival photograph of the Topulli House, showing the external architectural configuration within its historical urban context, alongside an interior view of the main room (oda burrave), highlighting its traditional spatial layout and integrated timber furnishings; b) Recent images showing the current state of preservation, structural alterations, and material degradation (Source: IKTK-Archive).

The house is most renowned as the birthplace of Çerçiz Topulli (1880–1915), a prominent figure in the Albanian National Awakening. Alongside his brother Bajo, he led one of the first armed bands against Ottoman forces in southern Albania. Their assassination of the Ottoman commander Halil Musa Bey in 1908 and the subsequent Battle of Mashkullorë marked key moments in the nationalist movement [28, 29]. In 1967, the residence was converted into the National Awakening Museum, initiated by museologist Lefter Dilo. It displayed artifacts linked to Topulli and the broader independence struggle. Although officially titled the Museum of National Renaissance, it remains widely known as the Çerçiz Topulli Museum [15, 28] (see Fig. 1a). While parts of the house are still inhabited by descendants, preservation efforts remain limited, and structural degradation poses ongoing challenges (see Fig. 1b).

ARCHITECTURAL SURVEY, SITE WORK INSTRUMENTS AND METHODOLOGY

Architectural survey

The surveying of historic buildings constitutes an indispensable stage in the restoration workflow, providing the critical empirical foundation upon which all subsequent project interventions depend. It is imperative that extant documentation comprising preliminary sketches, architectural drawings, and previously acquired geometric measurements be meticulously synthesized with newly collected observational data. This integration must be executed through a systematic, methodical framework to produce a coherent, structured, and comprehensive dataset. Such rigorously compiled data serves not only as a reliable baseline for the ongoing design and planning phases but also as an authoritative reference that supports informed decision-making throughout the restoration process. Ensuring the precision, consistency, and traceability of this combined information is essential to uphold the scientific and technical standards required for the successful preservation and rehabilitation of historic structures [22].

Fig. 2. Integrated on-site data acquisition procedures for the digital survey of the Topulli House: a) UAV-based photogrammetry using DJI Mavic 3E for contextual 3D modeling and orthophotos; b) Manual sketches and metric measurements to validate non-digital data; c) Terrestrial LiDAR scanning with FJD Trion P1 for high-precision façade geometry; d) Real-time point-cloud monitoring within the FJD platform for in-situ data validation.

Digital Surveying Methods and Detail Extraction: Current State and Technological Tools

Another important aspect is the level of detail, which must be appropriately represented in the final product. To make a well-founded decision in this regard, the input of an expert user is essential. A survey product whether a line drawing or an image inevitably involves a certain degree of generalization. Therefore, the criteria and boundaries of this generalization must be carefully defined, always in close collaboration with the architect, who possesses in-depth knowledge of the monument [13].

For geometric registration, a range of surveying methods can be employed, spanning from basic topometric techniques to advanced contemporary surveying and photogrammetric approaches. Traditionally, due to financial limitations and scientific obligations, simpler topometric methods were favored. However, negative outcomes associated with these techniques, coupled with technological advancements in surveying and photogrammetry, as well as prevailing international trends, have driven a fundamental shift in this approach [34].

Actually, the geometric survey of cultural heritage monuments utilizes two principal categories of methods:

- Simplified topometric approaches, often applied in cases where full survey control is not feasible or necessary, generally serving preliminary documentation or rapid assessment needs;
- High-precision techniques such as LiDAR scanning and photogrammetry, which facilitate fully controlled spatial data acquisition, ensuring detailed and accurate geometric representations essential for restoration planning, structural analysis, and long-term heritage conservation [2, 5, 7, 13, 22] (Fig. 2a); Basic topometric methods are applied selectively and only in situations where the monument's scale and structural simplicity justify their use typically in cases where limited precision is acceptable or when they serve as a supplementary tool to enhance more advanced surveying approaches. Conversely, modern techniques such as terrestrial photogrammetry and LiDAR-based surveying are grounded in the accurate acquisition of linear and angular measurements, either from the physical structure or its visual representations. These methods enable the reconstruction of three-dimensional spatial data within a unified coordinate system, ensuring a high degree of geometric reliability and reproducibility [2, 5, 7, 13, 22, 34]. Beyond their technical accuracy, these methodologies offer distinct operational benefits, including versatility in application, rapid data acquisition, enhanced safety in fieldwork, and overall procedural efficiency. Crucially, from an economic perspective, they demonstrate clear cost-effectiveness, often emerging as the most viable solution for comprehensive heritage documentation by minimizing resource expenditure while maximizing data quality and utility [13, 22].
- Advanced Scanning methods of built heritage using FJD Trion laser: The scanning and documentation of historic buildings increasingly leverages cutting-edge LiDAR scanning technology, such as the FJD Trion P1 laser scanner, to achieve highly detailed spatial records (see Fig. 2c, 2d). This portable 3D laser scanner employs real-time

SLAM^[1] technology, enabling rapid acquisition of up to 320,000 points per second with a spatial accuracy of around ± 2 centimeters [37]. These features make it particularly effective for capturing the complex geometries typical of heritage architecture. Data collected by the scanner is exported into standard point cloud file formats like LAS, PLY, or E57, which can be processed through dedicated software including FJD Smart LiDAR or popular third-party tools like Cloud Compare and Autodesk Recap [14, 18, 34, 37]. The processed point clouds are then incorporated into Building Information Modeling (BIM) systems through specialized point cloud-to-BIM workflows, facilitating the creation of precise 3D models that support conservation planning and management (see Fig. 5). Integrating these advanced scanning techniques with BIM significantly enhances the precision, efficiency, and comprehensiveness of built heritage documentation and preservation strategies [1, 3, 5, 14, 18, 34, 37].

VERNACULAR ARCHITECTURE OF GJIROKASTRA AND THE CASE OF CERCIZ TOPULLI HOUSE

Gjirokastra house typology and architectural elements

Characteristics and elements of Gjirokastër Houses and Architectural Design Influenced by Ottoman Style: Many tower-type house typologies in Gjirokastër date from the late Ottoman period. These buildings exhibit greater refinement compared to earlier versions, incorporating certain stylistic elements derived from the Ottoman Rococo of the era; however, their defensive characteristics remain prominently visible [4, 6, 10].

The city's location on a steep, uneven rocky mountainside imposed significant constraints on construction; nevertheless, the selection of such a challenging site was a deliberate strategic decision. A 19th-century English traveler observed that rival families erected their towers in disadvantageous locations such as valleys and rocky outcrops where they could sustain their disputes over extended periods without any decisive resolution [10, 17].

Externally, Gjirokastra houses appear exceptionally robust and austere, with massive stone walls. These walls, typically tall and somewhat narrow in plan, convey a formidable, fortress like impression (see Fig. 3). Stone, as the most durable locally available construction material of the time, dominates the urban fabric: house walls were built from rectangular stone blocks meticulously carved by skilled artisans, roofs were clad with flat grey stone slabs, and streets were paved with stone cobblestones [15, 19, 34].

The presence and height of one or more chimneys held symbolic significance. Only affluent families were permitted to construct chimneys on their roofs; the greater the chimney's height, the higher the family's social status. The lower floors featured bare walls constructed from exposed stone masonry without plaster or decorative cladding. Architectural ornamentation was minimal. Despite limited enforcement by the Ottoman administration regarding minimum window opening sizes on façades, windows on the lower levels were either very small or altogether absent [28, 29]. When present, these openings were arched and functioned defensively as embrasures. (see Fig. 3) [15, 28, 34]

¹ Note: Simultaneous Localization and Mapping technology.

Fig. 3. BIM-based reconstruction of the Topulli House illustrating key phases of architectural transformation: a) Archival-based BIM model representing the original 19th-century configuration; b) BIM model reflecting alterations from the communist era, including façade modifications; c) Current condition model documenting structural deterioration and material loss; d) Proposed revitalization scenario integrating recovered vernacular features to restore architectural authenticity. Detail views (Part 1 & 2) emphasize typological elements of Gjirokastra’s vernacular architecture, such as musandara, testeke, and stained-glass fenestration, as captured through heritage-informed modeling strategies.

Construction techniques in Berat and Gjirokastrë exhibit a synthesis of indigenous Albanian and Ottoman influences. The robust stone masonry employed on the ground floors traces back to the traditional Albanian rural defensive tower known as the “kullë”. In contrast, the upper levels incorporate a timber-framed system (çatma), complemented by wooden laths and plaster finishes, as well as a series of window openings and balconies. These elements reflect the characteristics of Ottoman urban architectural practices (Fig. 3) [6, 26, 28, 29]. The predominant construction material in the city is locally sourced stone, utilized extensively in the fabrication of walls, roofing, street pavements, and courtyards. These elements are primarily composed of limestone blocks or slabs alongside native shale deposits [19, 28, 29, 34, 35]. Timber serves a crucial role in structural reinforcement, being employed in masonry support, as well as in the frameworks of floors, roofs, and upper wall sections.

Architectural Context and Vernacular Elements of the Topulli House

The Topulli House exemplifies the single tower-type vernacular architecture. Its composition reflects the typical tripartite structure of fortified Albanian dwellings, with a robust masonry ground floor and lighter timber-framed upper levels (see Fig. 3). The stone base constructed from irregularly coursed local limestone served utilitarian functions such as storage, stabling, and wine or food preservation. In contrast, the upper floors exhibit more refined spatial and material treatments, featuring plastered timber frames, extensive fenestration, and wide overhanging eaves (testek), supported by timber rafters anchored into the masonry [4, 10]. These eaves (extending 50–60 cm) are a key regional trait, protecting façades and enhancing climatic performance [26] (Fig. 3).

The primary façade, oriented north toward the bazaar, demonstrates the social significance of architectural ornament and visibility in Gjirokastrë’s domestic tradition (see Fig. 1a). It incorporates tall, multi-pane windows, once integrated within a double-story wooden loggia, reconstructed in the recent restoration. This element historically expressed wealth and status through its spatial prominence and crafted timber detailing. Roofing consists of a steeply pitched stone-slab covering typical of the region, laid over timber rafters extending outward to form deep eaves. Decorative friezes under the eaves and wooden shutters have been reinstated to reflect the original aesthetic. The limited fenestration on the secondary façades underlines the defensive and climatic logic of the vernacular type [24, 26].

Internally, the spatial organization follows a simple central circulation scheme. The ground floor contains the stera (entry hall and rainwater catchment), paved in large stone flags and lit by narrow arched openings. Flanking this space are plain vaulted rooms serving as stables or storage. Timber stairs lead to the upper level, which hosts the oda e burrave (men’s guest room), distinguished by a prominent stone fireplace and decorative cabinetry (dollar). Materials include lime-plastered walls, wood-beamed ceilings, and locally sourced carved stone elements (Fig. 3) [34].

Historical Evolution and Transformations of the Topulli House

The Topulli House, constructed in the late 19th century by the Topulli family, exemplified the defensive and domestic vernacular of Gjirokastër's tower typology. The structure manifesting both structural ingenuity and symbolic authority. Internally, its carved woodwork, stone arches, and ornamented ceilings reflected a synthesis of craftsmanship and social function (Fig. 3a) [6, 10].

During the early 20th century, the house served as a residence and discreet meeting site for nationalist leaders Çerçiz and Bajo Topulli. World War II inflicted major damage, especially due to fire in the 1940s, reducing the upper structure to a ruinous shell. Restoration commenced in 1967 under the communist regime, repurposing the house as the Museum of the National Renaissance. Although partially reconstructed, the restoration prioritized ideological messaging over architectural fidelity, simplifying original forms, plastering façades, and removing distinctive structural elements such as *testekët* (Fig.3, detail 6) [28, 29].

Subsequent alterations in the 1970s further homogenized the building's expression, replacing vernacular materials with standardized components (Fig. 3b). After 1991, the building was returned to the Topulli house, falling into partial neglect and informal residential use. By the 2010s, minimal conservation occurred, and degradation of wooden features continued.

In 2020, a municipal agreement-initiated effort for formal musealization, marking a paradigm shift toward integrated heritage stewardship (Fig. 3c). Presently, the house operates as both a semi-public museum and a lived-in residence, incorporating modest interventions secondary entrances, essential amenities without compromising the structural integrity or authenticity of the original timber and stone elements. This coexistence underscores a rare model of heritage continuity: an adaptive space balancing conservation, commemoration, and contemporary habitation.

CURRENT CONDITION, FUNCTIONAL ALTERATIONS, AND MATERIAL PATHOLOGIES

The Topulli House retains its historical character and spatial configuration, representing a critical example of Gjirokastër's vernacular fortified dwellings. While the original form remains legible, the structure has undergone a series of incremental interventions reflecting shifts in function and material adaptation [17]. These changes ranging from spatial reconfiguration to selective material substitutions demonstrate a dynamic balance between preservation ethics and evolving user needs.

One notable alteration is the insertion of a secondary access point on the rear façade, introduced by the resident family. A minimally-roofed transitional volume was appended at ground level, enabling a private entrance distinct from the main museum access. This adaptation underscores contemporary spatial negotiations between private residency and public heritage function. Although spatially modest, the intervention redefines circulation hierarchies and reflects modern living requirements absent from the original plan [28, 29].

Internally, most rooms retain their original dimensions and intended functions, though selective updates such as aluminum window frames and the loss of stained-glass elements reflect thermal performance upgrades and maintenance constraints. The removal of significant architectural components, including the *çatma* framing and *testekë* (timber eaves), has diminished both the tectonic clarity and visual legibility of the façades.

Material assessments identified pronounced deterioration, especially along the northeast façade, attributed to inadequate solar exposure and persistent atmospheric moisture. Pathological manifestations include biological colonization (moss, mold), plaster delamination from rising damp, salt efflorescence, staining, root intrusions and structural cracking around fenestrations (see Fig. 4) [19, 21]. These are consistent with age-induced decay in hybrid masonry buildings, exacerbated by previous unsympathetic repairs and systemic maintenance neglect.

Fig. 4. Current pathological analysis conducted on the façades of the Topulli House, identifying material deterioration, structural anomalies, and signs of environmental damage

Overall, the building illustrates the dual pressures of heritage preservation and functional adaptation. While core structural systems persist, selective material and spatial interventions reflect a continuous negotiation between authenticity, performance, and domestic utility [9].

BIM-Based Architectural Analysis and Restoration Strategy

A Building Information Modeling (BIM) framework was developed in Autodesk Revit to document, analyze, and simulate the conservation needs of the Topulli House. The model integrates data derived from photogrammetric point clouds and terrestrial 3D laser scans (FJD), enabling precise alignment between historical documentation and current structural conditions [3, 5, 7, 16, 36]. The parametric model reflects the architectural stratigraphy of the 19th-century building, including traditional Gjirokastra elements such as stone masonry walls, “musandara” (built-in wooden cupboards), stained-glass fenestration, and “testeke” (projecting wooden eaves) [22, 23]. These culturally embedded elements were classified and modeled as Revit families for accurate representation and scheduling (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. BIM architectural evolution model in Revit: (a) original 19th-century elements including stone masonry and stained glass; (b) 1940s interventions with plastered masonry, testeke (exposed timber beams), wooden frames and window alterations reflecting progressive material degradation; (c) current state marked by aluminum window replacements, façade moisture damage, cracking, and loss of testeke (timber components); (d) restoration proposal focused on reinstating original materials and features wooden windows, testeke, stained glass and cleaning masonry to restore structural authenticity and heritage value.

Chronological transformations, particularly those occurring post-1940, were incorporated into the model to assess the degradation of authenticity over time. Modifications such as cement plastering, removal of traditional features, and installation of

Structural Modeling Using ETABS v22: using F.E.M. Modelling

The structural analysis was independently carried out using ETABS v22, separate from the BIM modeling workflow (see Fig. 7a). The model was based on architectural plans and survey data derived from the current condition of the building, captured using the FJD Trion P1 laser scanner. This approach ensured a high level of geometric accuracy, critical for reliable structural simulation. The modeling primarily focused on the stone masonry walls, incorporating vertical reductions and accounting for the presence of traditional infill elements such as “çatma” [2]. Floor systems were represented using Slab type: thin shell elements with timber joists, modeled in accordance with the on-site measurements and construction details observed on-site [21, 26, 29, 31]. Foundation conditions and soil–structure interaction were idealized through fixed joint supports at relevant elevations, based on the presence of continuous stone strip footings combined with lean concrete layers [29, 31]. These details were further informed by the site’s topographical gradient and subsurface soil characteristics (see Fig. 7a). A key aspect of the simulation involved the accurate assignment of material properties. The mechanical behavior of the stone and mortar was modeled using characteristic parameters derived from prior research and literature specific to historic masonry [31-36]. These material inputs were essential for representing the nonlinear and anisotropic response typical of vernacular heritage structures. Non-structural components, such as wood staircases and secondary roof layers, were introduced as static loads. The roof framework, characterized by irregular spatial trusses, was partially modeled, while later structural additions were included as supplementary loading (see Fig. 7a). Service loads and superimposed dead loads, including finishing layers and flooring systems, were incorporated in accordance with Eurocode load standards [12, 26, 29, 31, 34].

a)

² Note: A timber-framed wall filled with a lightweight infill material such as stone rubble, adobe, or mud brick, often plastered over. This technique is part of Ottoman vernacular architecture and is commonly known across the Balkans and Anatolia.

b)

Fig. 7. a) Geometric representation of the 3D finite element model in ETABS; b) Stress distribution diagram along the principal axes of the stone masonry walls.

A sequence of finite element simulations was performed. An initial static analysis assessed the structure's current performance and stability. This was followed by a seismic analysis, simulating the response under the load combinations, as prescribed by contemporary Eurocode provisions [11, 12, 27] (see Fig. 7b). The seismic assessment provided insight into the vulnerability of specific structural components and allowed for the evaluation of stress distribution throughout the entire building envelope [21, 31] (see Fig. 7b). Numerical results included internal force diagrams and stress contour plots, offering valuable data for diagnosing structural deficiencies. These outputs form the basis for developing a targeted seismic retrofitting strategy, a critical intervention step in the structural rehabilitation and conservation of historic buildings within the framework of cultural heritage preservation.

Revitalization and Adaptive Reuse Strategy: “Penë dhe Plumba” (Quills and Bullets). A Heritage-Driven Cultural Reimagining

The initiative outlines a comprehensive revitalization strategy for the historic Topulli House, converting it into a dynamic cultural and historical museum that reflects the tangible and intangible heritage of the Gjirokastra region. This project prioritizes the preservation of the building's architectural and cultural identity while promoting active public engagement (see Fig. 8). Departing from conventional conservation paradigms, it reimagines the house as an interactive environment, leveraging immersive technologies such as Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) to facilitate physical, emotional, and intellectual visitor interaction [22, 36].

The visitor journey commences on the fully operational ground floor, dedicated to historical interpretation. This space integrates preserved stone masonry, authentic porticos, original mural fragments, and remaining architectural details that collectively embody the building’s original fabric. Advanced audiovisual installations and projection mapping techniques reconstruct critical historical episodes, delivering an immersive multisensory narrative (see Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 Summarized images of the proposed revitalization strategy for the historic Topulli House, developed through BIM using Revit software.

The project also reinstates the traditional Gjirokastra kitchen as a living exhibit, enabling experiential engagement with local culinary heritage. Adjacent artisanal workshops provide hands-on access to traditional crafts, spotlighting local master artisans and preserving vernacular production techniques once practiced on-site. These elements enrich the

first-floor program, layering cultural education with tangible heritage. On the second floor, focus shifts to the meticulous architectural and symbolic restoration of the “oda e burrave” (men’s guest room), a quintessential element of Gjirokastra vernacular housing. Reconstructed based on archival documentation, this space features authentic wooden elements including intricately carved ceiling rosettes, built-in wardrobes, and musandara cabinetry. The intervention emphasizes material fidelity and artisanal detail to recover lost heritage and reinstate the room’s cultural significance (see Fig. 8) [22]. Throughout, all conservation and restoration interventions are rigorously aligned with international charters, emphasizing retention of original spatial organization and material authenticity [30]. This ensures the Topulli House’s historical integrity is preserved while enabling its sustainable reuse as a culturally vibrant public asset.

CONCLUSIONS

This study proposes a multidisciplinary methodology for the documentation, analysis, and structural assessment of vernacular architecture, with a focus on the Çerçiz Topulli House in Gjirokastra. It demonstrates how combining historical research, digital technologies, and structural modeling enables a more comprehensive and context-sensitive approach to conservation in seismically active and topographically complex urban heritage sites. From an architectural and heritage perspective, the research reaffirms the cultural and typological value of Gjirokastra’s historic dwellings. These fortified stone houses with timber-framed upper floors (çatma), carved stone detailing, and slate roofs exemplify a sophisticated synthesis of Ottoman design principles and local construction traditions. Preserving such structures demands careful attention not only to individual elements but also to the urban coherence of the ensemble and the socio-historical layers it represents.

The integration of advanced documentation technologies specifically, terrestrial photogrammetry, the FJD Trion P1 mobile LiDAR scanner, and Building Information Modeling (BIM) has proven essential for capturing the building’s current condition with high spatial accuracy. The FJD Trion P1, utilizing real-time SLAM technology, enabled rapid and detailed 3D data acquisition, while photogrammetry supported texture-rich visual reconstruction of the architectural envelope. This multi-sensor approach produced a precise, data-rich point cloud, which was subsequently processed into a BIM environment. The BIM model served as a central platform for managing geometric, material, and structural information, facilitating not only documentation but also analytical interpretation and restoration planning.

In the realm of structural engineering, finite element analysis using ETABS based on the BIM-integrated point cloud data allowed for realistic simulation of the building’s seismic behavior. The model incorporated historic material properties, structural anisotropy, and site-specific boundary conditions. Stress distribution patterns and internal force diagrams identified critical vulnerabilities, thereby informing the development of a targeted structural retrofitting strategy. This approach balances technical intervention with cultural sensitivity, ensuring that reinforcement measures do not compromise the historical integrity of the structure.

The “Pen and Bullets” revitalization project demonstrates a progressive shift in cultural heritage restoration toward an immersive and participatory experience. By restoring lost architectural features and incorporating advanced VR and AR technologies, the project safeguards the Topulli House’s cultural identity while actively engaging visitors. The precise rehabilitation of critical spatial typologies most notably the “oda e burrave” strengthens the vernacular architectural narrative, highlighting material authenticity and artisanal detail. Strict compliance with international restoration standards ensures interventions remain minimal, reversible, and faithful to the original fabric. This integrated approach, combining digital documentation, structural evaluation, and innovative museology within an adaptive reuse framework, offers a robust and replicable methodology for vernacular heritage preservation in Albania and similar contexts, promoting the sustainable conservation and revitalization of cultural landmarks.

In conclusion, the research advocates for a holistic digital heritage workflow in which BIM modeling, LiDAR scanning, and photogrammetry are not merely tools for documentation but foundational components in structural diagnosis, retrofit planning, and long-term conservation. This methodology provides a replicable model for similar interventions in heritage structures across the Balkans and other regions with comparable vernacular traditions and conservation challenges.

Beyond the case-specific findings, this study also informs wider policy and educational agendas. At the conservation policy level, it demonstrates the value of integrating digital workflows BIM, LiDAR, and photogrammetry into regulatory frameworks for heritage management and seismic risk mitigation. In Higher Education, it highlights how these tools strengthen digital literacy and analytical capacity, preparing future professionals to address heritage challenges with both technical rigor and cultural sensitivity.

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